

INSTAR

CEI-Sphere

POST-EVENT REPORT

Cross-Domain Standardisation and Architecture for IoT and Edge Computing

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Cross-Domain Standardisation and Architecture for IoT and Edge Computing

The “**Workshop on Cross-Domain Standardisation and Architecture for IoT and Edge Computing**” took place on 26-27 November 2024 in Brussels, organised by the **European Commission** in collaboration with the **CEI-Sphere** and **INSTAR** projects.

This event convened policymakers and key stakeholders from industry and academia to address the critical role of standardisation in advancing the EU’s leadership in the global digital ecosystem. Discussions also highlighted practical challenges, such as system integration and the shift from cloud to edge, as well as the importance of collaborative approaches to achieve interoperability and scalability.

INSTAR an EU-funded Coordination and Support Action (CSA), supports Europe’s Digital Partnerships and the EU-US TTC by collaborating with global partners to advance ICT standards in 5G+/6G, AI, Cybersecurity/eID, Data Technologies, IoT/Edge/Cloud, and Quantum Technologies—key enablers of future innovation.

Launched in October 2024, **CEI-Sphere**, another EU-funded CSA, aims to strengthen the European Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI) ecosystem by addressing industry challenges through Large-Scale Pilots (LSPs).

CEI-Sphere, officially launched in October 2024, is also an EU-funded CSA that aims to strengthen the European Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI) ecosystem by addressing emerging industry challenges, particularly through Large-Scale Pilots (LSPs). Its goals include fostering collaboration among LSPs, generating market insights to bridge adoption gaps, promoting privacy-

preserving open ecosystems, developing toolkits for scalable and interoperable solutions, and expanding stakeholder engagement to enhance community growth and visibility.

Featuring contributions from leading organisations such as the Telecommunications Technology Association, xFlow Research and Standards, BDVA, CEN/CENELEC, ETSI, W3C, JRC Sevilla, Citycom.AI, ECOS, VIESSMANN, WIKA Alexander Wiegand SE & Co, Nibe Industrier, eebus, Digital4Grids, ECLIPSE, Foundation, Phoenix, International Hellenic University, and Siemens, the event offered participants insights into how standardisation can drive cross-domain innovation, enhance interoperability, and strengthen Europe’s digital infrastructure. Several key examples were provided, including some upcoming Cloud-Edge-IoT pilots, which cover diverse applications from energy distribution and autonomous tractors to Electric Vehicle (EV) charging and citizen engagement in smart cities. These pilots aim to deliver scalable, replicable blueprints for various industries.

INSTAR / TTA Steering Board Launch Meeting

In parallel to the workshop, INSTAR was delighted to be able to host the first **Steering Board Launch meeting INSTAR / TTA – Telecommunications Technology Association, KR** on day 1 26th November with members from the Global Standards Cooperation Centre and Standardisation Division at TTA, who attended the in-person meeting especially to discuss how to drive forward the **EU-South Korea dialogue**, on sharing mutual roadmaps, understanding priorities and gaps for the future especially around testing, conformity assessments and routes to understanding the adoption of best practices.

This event served as a practical follow up to the MoU signing between TTA & INSTAR project, back in September 2024, to help strengthen the **EU-South Korea Digital Partnership**. A joint hybrid workshop will be organized in **March 2025**, to consolidate some of the ideas that were agreed upon during the Steering board.

The event explored the intersection between international standards, emerging technologies, and global collaboration. At its core, the event emphasised the critical role of standardisation in ensuring that Europe's industry remains competitive, a vital factor for safeguarding economic resilience. Stakeholders were urged to adapt their strategies to align with shifting global dynamics, ensuring that contractual obligations and technological approaches remain relevant in an ever-changing

landscape. The challenges of system integration, including embedding systems and software-defined architectures, were frequently highlighted, underscoring the importance of multi-layered approaches spanning hardware, middleware, and applications.

The discussions also tackled the geopolitical implications of standardisation, highlighting the challenges posed by rising tensions between major global players such as the US and China. These tensions underline the need for Europe to assert its role as a global leader in standardisation while securing its technological sovereignty. To achieve this, Europe must navigate the complexities of diverging global approaches by prioritising collaboration and strengthening its strategic alliances.

A unified European approach to international standardisation was deemed essential, ensuring that collective efforts amplify Europe's influence while aligning with like-minded global partners to shape the future of technology and industry collaboratively.

One of the transformative trends discussed during the workshop was the emergence of platform-based ecosystems, which are becoming vital tools for multi-stakeholder collaboration. These platforms, prioritising interoperability, security, and scalability, represent a significant step forward in creating environments where devices and systems from diverse manufacturers can seamlessly interact. Speakers highlighted the importance of balancing open-source strategies with standardisation efforts to avoid vendor lock-in and support sustainable ecosystems. Successful examples like EVerest's open-source EV charging stack, which is now globally adopted under the Linux Foundation Energy, were shared as case studies. Beyond platforms, the event also emphasised the necessity of cross-sector collaboration, especially in integrating previously siloed industries such as energy, mobility, and telecommunications. Harmonising these verticals and enabling shared data ecosystems were presented as critical to unlocking the full potential of standardisation and innovation.

Among the examples shared, the CODECO project showcased its flexible edge-cloud continuum and decentralised orchestration framework, while Nephele focused on virtualisation of IoT devices and synergetic orchestration frameworks. Similarly, the aerOS project demonstrated its innovative meta-operating system designed for the IoT edge-cloud continuum, integrating multiple standards to avoid vendor lock-in and ensure platform-agnostic solutions.

The workshop concluded by offering a series of critical insights and actionable outcomes that underscore the transformative potential of standardisation. At the forefront was the recognition of interoperability through standards as a cornerstone for integrating technologies such as AI, Digital Twins, and IoT into cohesive and sustainable systems.

A central theme was the EU's commitment to promoting European standards globally, extending efforts beyond like-minded partners to encourage the broader adoption of its standards. This ambition was supported by the essential role of real-world testing and industry-led pilots, which

will provide invaluable feedback for refining standards and ensuring their practical adoption, while the ICT Rolling Plan was identified as a key resource for guiding ongoing efforts.

As technology evolves rapidly with innovations like generative AI and 6G, the importance of adapting to technological advancements through flexible, decentralised solutions was strongly underscored. This adaptability must be complemented by collaborative synergies across European projects, fostering a culture of cooperation and avoiding redundant efforts. The EU's focus on ecosystem-building, as seen in initiatives like INSTAR, CEI-Sphere, HSbooster.eu, StandICT.eu, InDiCo Global, aims to empower all actors, including SMEs and start-ups through open calls, funding opportunities, and fostering collaboration across academia, industry, and standardisation bodies to deliver scalable, interoperable solutions that drive measurable impact in real-world applications.

Event

Takeaways:

Efforts are needed to advance EU digital norms and standards on a global scale, positioning the EU as a leader in international digital governance, with a particular focus on AI and cybersecurity.

A unified approach to IoT standardisation in Europe is essential to address geopolitical and competitive challenges. Collaboration and alignment among European actors on an international level strengthen collective influence and safeguard European interests.

Europe should collaborate not only with like-minded partners but also with counterparts worldwide to foster alignment in international standardisation, and engage on a global scale to influence standards, while promoting EU competitiveness and technological sovereignty.

EU-funded projects benefit from adopting a bottom-up approach, ensuring that relevant communities, industries, and stakeholders play an active role in advising the European Commission on potential areas of international cooperation.

Standardising machine-readable dictionaries and terminology facilitates cross-domain collaboration and ensures that engineers have access to and can interpret data, as demonstrated in applications such as the digital product passports.

Event

Takeaways:

Interoperability of standards provides the common foundation needed for interoperability across all other Cloud-Edge-IoT levels, including concepts, architectures, and systems.

The Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum lacks a comprehensive conformity framework. The “CEI Trust Label” integrates existing schemes to ensure trust and interoperability, providing an end-to-end solution for emerging technologies.

The energy sector is evolving towards decentralised systems with many small-scale energy producers and active, bidirectional participation of consumers in energy production and distribution.

Standards play a vital role in developing interoperable solutions that enable cross-sector collaboration. To bridge gaps in standardisation, it is essential to foster cooperation among industries, academia, and policymakers.

Piloting and real-world testing of standards not only accelerates their adoption but also ensures continuous refinement to meet evolving needs, as the future of interoperability relies on dynamic standards that can evolve alongside technological advancements. By fostering open and collaborative ecosystems, the EU will strengthen its industries’ global competitiveness.

Highlights

from our Speakers:

Max Lemke, Head of Unit for Internet of Things, EC DG CNECT, E4:

"Standardisation means collective commitment & cooperation, people have to adopt the standards & seamlessly integrate in the existing ecosystem. We need a culture of collaboration"

Svetoslav Mihaylov, Policy Officer for Internet of Things, EC DG CNECT, E4:

"We need to define gaps using or improving existing standards. Our approach must balance alignment with international interests and safeguarding our values and requirements, while adapting to regional differences and legislation such as the Data Act and Cybersecurity Act."

Rolf Riemenschneider, Head of Sector for Internet of Things, EC DG CNECT, E4:

"The complexity of IoT and edge computing demands a system-level approach. Platforms, pilots, and international collaboration are the building blocks for achieving Europe's technological sovereignty."

Carlos López-Rodríguez, Policy Officer of the European Commission, DG CNECT D3:

"We shouldn't only cooperate with our like-minded partners, but also with international partners all over the world to facilitate an alignment in international standardisation, and engage globally to influence international standards while promoting EU competitiveness and technological sovereignty."

Highlights

from our Speakers:

Tanya Suárez, CEO of BluSpecs:

"The synergy between open-source communities and standardisation efforts is a game-changer for driving innovation."

Henrik Madsen, DTU Compute:

"Demand-side flexibility powered by AI, Big Data, and IoT is key to aligning user energy consumption with renewable solutions, supported by standardisation and Minimum Interoperable Mechanisms (MIMs)."

Antonio Kung, Trialog:

"The value of standards lies in their adoption—unusable standards are as ineffective as having none."

Martin Roßmann, Technical Senior Advisor, VIESSMANN:

"We develop cloud-based solutions with an algorithm that determines potential of shiftable load in dependence of consumption forecast, building class, user behaviour, summation per network node."

Dave Raggett, W3C/ERCIM:

"We need clean, simple, easy to understand approaches that hide the underlying complexity of this process. Descriptions in terms of classes, properties and relationships, a behaviour modelled in terms of events, facts and rules to encourage the realisation of the benefits of the IoT."

Insights from the experts:

Laurent Schmitt, Digital4Grids:

"Interoperability is key, as grid operators use Digital Twins to standardise interfaces, focusing on applying existing standards to enable edge-operating devices and manage flexibility."

Dario Sabella, xFlow Research and Standards, Chair ETSI MEC:

"Do not try to re-invent the wheel. By reusing and avoiding over-standardisation, we ensure standards have practical uptake and impact."

Carlos Palau, Professor, Universitat Politècnica de València:

"Our focus is on enabling real-world adoption of edge solutions through flexibility, scalability, and interoperability. By embedding standards and developing replicable blueprints, we aim to provide adaptable solutions that can thrive across diverse sectors while avoiding vendor lock-in."

Gael Blondelle, Chief Membership Officer, ECLIPSE Foundation:

"Open standards and open source are two sides of the same coin. By providing royalty-free standards to open-source projects, we ensure broader adoption and create ecosystems that drive innovation."

Tim Valbert, VP of Product Management, Pionix:

"Open source is not just a methodology; it's a strategy for scalability. Everest's success as the leading open-source EV charging stack proves that openness fosters global adoption and interoperability."

Watch the recording

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INSTAR is an EU-funded CSA that aims to support Europe's Digital Partnerships and the EU-US TTC by collaborating with Australia, Canada, Japan, Singapore, South Korea, Taiwan, and the USA to advance international standards for emerging technologies. INSTAR'S goal is to cultivate a unified vision and develop strategic roadmaps for ICT standards in 5G+/6G, AI, Cybersecurity/eID, Data Technologies, IoT/Edge/Cloud/Internet and Quantum Technologies, as critical enablers of future innovation.

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